

To President of Pakistan. (Formality)

To Crown Prince of KSA.

To President of Russia.

To President of China.

To President of Japan.

To UN. (Formality)

To UNHCR (Formality)

Traitor COAS ASIM MUNIR. Traitor of Islam, Traitor of Pakistan, Traitor of Allah, Rasool SAW, QURAN And it's Pakistan Army and his companions. Head of terrorism in Pakistan, mastermind of 9 May illegal activities, Head of Gullu butts and most evil person in Pakistan. Including Present DG ISI worker of Present traitor. I can cut your heads anytime by giving proves to the world 🌐 that Asim Munir given several my patented technologies of unmanned stealth sub marines of 2 types. Only reconnaissance small but long endurance sub marines equipped with small nuke to sink any air Craft carrier, optional and 2nd larger size but unmanned stealth by propulsion technology and especially undetectable while doing communication with Command Post via satellite, maritime patrol crafts and trasmit and received Data. But this is head line of my research work. I can release data anytime to end Asim Munir. But i set several different dates and times from US and non US Platforms with over 2 dozen accounts. Not now. I did that months ago. Even if i try to stop all those things to spread world wide i need atleast 5,6 hours.

But these conditions. If they are fulfilled then your life can be saved.

- 1- Release Imran Khan and he must continue his government from where your terrorist company taken forcfully. He must be released immediately within 24 hours. And as he is elected prime minister he do not need new elections until he complete his 5 years. Your puppits Prime Ministers Shehbaz Shareef or kukar are not acceptable.
- 2- Release and restore Dr. Afia Siddiqui to her home in Pakistan. You son of prostitutes, your general mushraf accepted that he sold Dr. Afia Siddiqui to USA. But no media will be allowed to go and interview her. And apology letter From entire Pakistan army for Dr. Afia Siddiqui to me, which i will bring to her and ask for forgiveness for crimes of Pakistan Army.
- 3- Immediate sentence of death to chief justice Qazi Faiz essa and must be hanged outside supreme court in crime of betraying Allah, Rasool Allah SAW, along with Molana Tariq Jameel of same crime.
- 4- All bureaucracy of Pakistan will be changed with A.I.
- 5- Pakistani Nation never taken any debts from evil banks and organizations of the worlds IMF, World bank, Asian development bank. If any loan is taken behind every crime there are Pak army Generals. And these generals will pay all drbitFrom their reserves in foreign banks. Which is over 800 billion USD.
- 6- Pakistan Nation will pay fix rate of Electricity including all taxes Rs. 10/unite PKR. And Rs. 80/litre for petrol and Rs. 82/litre for Diesel, 1/10th of yesterday gas prices. Rs. 60/ kg of LPG.
- 7- Replacement of Russian Embassy with USA's embassy. With only 3person staff of US embassy. Kick all other us emassy members in Arabian sea near fake dead body of Osama bin Ladin.

- 8- All HEC and PEC officials and bureaucrats will clean roads and sewers of Pindi and other cities of Pakistan under staff of cleaning workers. It is most better job than what they are doing now.
- 9- I don't want anything for me. I don't need your sluty money or any big post.
- 10- No ex military official will ever serve any civilian Department, university, college etc.
- 11- In case of i get asylum on my terms and conditions then i can forgive you. Otherwise famous quote of movie Titanic "You die, i die, together". Well because we don't love each other so we most probably die on different dates.
- 12- To Bureaucrats of C&W Department you will pay of my 14 years service and my father's car's service and operational charges plus fine total 1 billion SR. In next 48 hours after 48 hours 10% fine will be added every 24 hours. Try to delay as much as possible. Fine will increase. And then most robably i change SR to USD OR Kuwaiti dinar. This is not fine of your crimes and corruption. This is fine because in my official previous letter i just asked for operational charges of my father's car, because it was your duty to provide vehicle with petrol, even your secretary Musa Raza promised me to provide 4x4 and petrol monthly. But never given one liter of petrol. Now previous request time over. And it is not request. It's order, and i am always eady for next move.

My life and death belongs to Allah and i will return to him.

To all corrupt Bureaucracy of Pakistan and C&W Department. Non engineering folks doing corruption in Engineering Department just to do corruption. I contacted some A.I expert Companies of China, Their one A.I computer can do all works of bureaucracy and that consume only around 200 to 400 watts electricity less 1/10th than 1.5 ton AC. And one computer with A.I. can outperform these leeches, by speed, correct decisions, maximum hours duty. No leaves, no absence, 24/7 working, can read and analyze any short or lenthly reports and respond quickly with answer directly from connected printer. Can calculate, think, analyze much better and faster and keep all records in their memory and just one computer can perform duty of Chief Secretary Punjab, Secretaries of different departments, additional secretary , deputy secretaries, assistant secretaries. And much better i openly challenge all bureaucracy of Pakistan to open test of your abilities and A.I abilities. And A.I will fuck you in front of entire world 🌍. They are not arrogants like you, they work only. Zero corruption.

While you corrupt white elephants eat billions monthly illegally and legally by government of Pakistan near default Pakistan, and having luxury houses of government and expensive cars of Government with several thousand units of free electricity, Petrol, lot of peons, P.As compter staff because they are illiterate with fake degrees and passed CSS with corruption. That's why the support corruption. And their loyalties are with enemies of Islam and Pakistan. They are more evil than jews. Most of them directly worshipping Satan and performed satanic rituals. In Pakistan but especially in their USA, UK visits.

NAB. ACE. FIA. And all other corruption support departments. On Request to me yesterday by Chief Engineer Monitoring Punjab. C&W department. He heard rumors about corruption by previous chief engineer Wahla did passed Miyaan Chanoo Talamba road, project cost was 2 Billion. Inspected by me, Chief Engineer wahla, with mobile Laboratory on spot tested and sub Base failed badly, around 50 compression or less, then that Road XEN presented us 17 different kind dishes in nearest costly restaurant. After few days i heard rumors that road is passed by Chief Engineer wahla by taking 2.5 million, i quated about that rumor somewhere then chief engineer wahla sommoned me in Lahore in his office, and threatened me, abused me and dictated word by word to write forgiveness letter in which he

dictated write rumor was false... accidentally everything recorded in my mobile voice recorder clearly. First time i am revealing it. ON SPECIAL REQUEST OF CURRENT CHIEF ENGINEER MONITORING.

According to Collins Dictionary definition of Rumor is "A rumour is a story or piece of information that may or may not be true, but that people are talking about."

How can a rumor can be true or false? Without investigation? Funny people. Actually idiots. Now time to investigate about rumor was false or true. All intelligence agencies and investigation agencies.

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1PCPiGvsLq0DC4QTcY1Uyd-SDIj4tB-Lw/view?usp=drivesdk>

Punjab police Register FIR on this matter.

Civil and military intelligence. You know that i was the one who was sending my every report too you by one of your inspector. From day first.

All hypocrite Ullema Pakistani Islamic Scholars. Ask for forgiveness of Almighty and go do Jihad for Palestinian brothers and sisters.

Police department. I given you list of people with proves and reports ad one more name in it, Chief Engineer punjab Monitoring and evaluation, C&W Punjab, still you have not arrested a single culprit of many crimes, including attempt of murder crimes, i am giving you another chance, prove you are loyal to Allah, Rasool Allah SAW, Quran and Pakistan.

Judges and lawyers of Pakistan especially judges and lawyers of MULTAN, who will die in near future under building of New District Court Complex. 100% with guarantee. If you have any doubts do international level inquiry on your own building atleast and if you do justice then do inquiry.

All students studying in Pakistan colleges, universities if you want to be corrupt as these people then read what they given to you read. If you want to be true human beings, then read Quran and Sunnah, Bukhari, Muslim etc. No need to go to ullema fr your problems or corrupt officials for job. Allah is giver of food, wealth and respect. See Imran Khan is in Jail but Allah Almighty given him respect more than any leader of Muslim 🌍 but your present Chief of Army Staff Asim Munir respect is less then a takka.

FBR what is this type of income? Worth in trillions, annually with no tax on it. Put accountability on it. And 80% Tax on it. Because it comes completely free. Molanas, Darbars, peers etc for example,they do mot work. They work is for God, am i right? Ask them.

Previous Files.

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1hS8w5V789FDjIYpfFp205hN-G6DeaMO/view?usp=drivesdk>

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ar8BzIII-bIOnKPm30VLG0ikgn8okbxJ/view?usp=drivesdk>

6:13

Vol 1.41
LTE1 KB/s 4G 99%

Molana Tariq Jameel
online

6:25 pm ✓✓

25 September 2023

السلام عليكم محترم
کیا آپ مولانا طارق جمیل فاؤنڈیشن کے ایک لاکھ
ڈونر (جو ایک ہزار ماہانہ فاؤنڈیشن میں جمع کروائیں
گے) ان میں شمار ہونا چاہتے ہیں؟
آپ اپنا نام، ایڈریس اور موبائل نمبر سینڈ کر دیں تا
کہ آپ کی رجسٹریشن کی جائے۔

7:23 am

Is documents main meri details bhe likhi
hain.

9:09 am ✓✓

Today

To
President of Pakistan.
Prime Minister of Afghanistan.
Supreme Court of Afghanistan.
UN, UNHCR.
Head of States of All countries of the Worlds. Especially Friend Countries. Non US.

 To Entire World.pdf
4 pages • 163 kB • PDF

1:09 pm ✓✓

Molana Tariq Jameel

السلام عليكم محترم
کیا آپ مولانا طارق جمیل فاؤنڈیشن کے ایک لاکھ ڈونر
(جو ایک ہزار ماہانہ فاؤنڈیشن میں جمع کروائیں گے) ان ...

Kitnay billion Pakistani awaam say loot
leye?

Sirf andaza koye? Waisy he

2:42 pm

Message

IN THE LAHORE HIGH COURT MULTAN BENCH MULTAN.

FOR PRIVATE USE
13923
The Chief Justice
of Lahore High Court
Lahore Bench, Multan

W.P. No. 2163 /2023

Muhammad Usman Malik S/O Abdul Maalik, R/O House No.29,
Mohallah New Multan Colony, Block-W, Tehsil & District Multan (Sub
Engineer, Buildings Monitoring and Evaluation, Multan).

PETITIONER

- VERSUS

1. Government of Punjab through Chief Secretary C&W
Department, Punjab Lahore.
2. Secretary C & W Department, Punjab Lahore.
3. Secretary Planning & Development Punjab Lahore.
4. Chief Engineer M & E Lahore.
5. Shahzad Sami Director M & E Region, Multan.
6. Haider Ali XEN Buildings Department Multan.
7. Abu Bakar SDO Buildings Department, Multan.
8. Yousaf Tariq Sub Engineer Buildings Department, Multan.

RESPONDENTS

**WRIT PETITION UNDER ARTICLE 199 OF
THE CONSTITUTION OF ISLAMIC REPUBLIC
OF PAKISTAN 1973.**

Respectfully Sheweth,

1. That the name and addresses of the parties have correctly
been given in the head note of the petition for effecting service
and communications.
2. That the brief facts giving rise to the instant petition are that
the petitioner has been serving as Sub Engineer, Buildings

HCD/C-121
ORDER SHEET
LAHORE HIGH COURT, MULTAN BENCH,
MULTAN,
JUDICIAL DEPARTMENT

W. P. No. 2163 / 2023

Muhammad Usman Malik

Versus

GoP, etc.

S.No. of order/proceeding	Date of order/proceeding	Order with signatures of Judge, and that of parties or counsel, where necessary.
	13.02.2023	Malik Nasir Javaid, Advocate for the Petitioner.

Learned counsel for the Petitioner contends that the Petitioner is working as Sub-Engineer, Buildings Monitoring & Evaluation, Multan and as a part of his official responsibility, he has highlighted various violations with respect to ongoing five projects through an Application before Respondent No. 2 which has not been decided so far and seeks a direction for early decision of the same. The contentions of the Petitioner are duly listed in the Petition.

2. Accordingly, this Petition alongwith its annexures is converted into a representation and transmitted to Respondent No. 2 (Secretary C & W Department, Punjab Lahore), who is directed to decide the same alongwith Application appended thereto through a well-reasoned and speaking Order strictly in accordance with law, after hearing the Petitioner and all other concerned persons, expeditiously, preferably within a period of sixty (60) days from the date of receipt of certified copy of this Order, under intimation to the Deputy Registrar (Judicial) of this Court. In order to regulate further proceedings, the Petitioner shall appear before the said Respondent on 20.02.2023 at 11:00

A.M.

Disposed of.

(Abid Hussain Chattha)
Judge

6598

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13.02.23

213-422

3/9/23

SUPPLY SECTION

ARTICLE 87

COPY

3/9/23

Respectful Crown Prince Muhammad Bin Salman, Respectful President Putin and Respectful Prime Minister of China. Request for Asylum with any better job as full citizenship. I will select better offer for me to start new life peacefully. In Pakistan my life is not safe by Asim Munir.

I sent my previous reports all of you. I am ordinary man. Alone and sick due to several attempts of them to kill me by various methods. Proves in my reports. I am diploma Engineer with total 16 years experience in engineering, i am also a scientist and have strong grip of knowledge and ability to develop according to latest requirements, i have several non registered patents (mostly i don't have any money to register my research works. In medical science, military technology, agriculture technology, environment friendly energy (geo thermal, wind, tidal, solar, liquid sodium solar, mechanical, hydrogen as new energy replacement for cars, bigger batteries, ICE engines like Toyota Mirai (a underrated but big achievement of Toyota), different types of Surveys, Stellite and drones are used by my from years for mapping cities, monitoring sites (but our government never given me one litre of fuel or theodolite, even steel or plastic tape for measuring). Finding mineral deposits, land mines, and other various things.

i do everything from my salary and my father's old car ML2484 MAKE VARIANT CC, Suzuki Alto 1000cc model 2002 of Pakistan manufactured. And i am honest man so see my power, Allah Almighty thrown COAS ASIM Munir respect under my feet. All praises for Almighty. I am nothing without Him.

This time my total wealth is Rs. 170/- which is equal to 0.6 USD maybe. Funny? Yeah this is power of Almighty Allah. Now a monitoring engineer with 16+ years service in different government departments unsold, fear only Almighty Allah. No property or wealth anywhere in the world 🌍. But see wealth of my knowledge, honesty and Faith, this is original success.

I am ordinary man but brutally behaved by government of Pakistan. I want to live simply work creatively and without fighting or politics. In Pakistan i am fighting to do my duty with honesty and for survival. Nor i am political worker in any party nor related to any Sects of Islam. I am ordinary Muslim, i take guidance from Holy Quran and follow Sunnah, and Read Ahadith of Muhammad PBUH. SELF. And according to rules of Quran i cannot fight in war (Jihad) as i have asthma since childhood.

Well i am single man. No wife. No parents. No family. Maybe i marry in future but these days i hate all women on earth thanks to my first and 2nd ex wives, i given divorce to 2nd 2 months ago... 😊. I am just living nearly Dead body with no happiness in life but a hope for better.

Muhammad Usman Malik

Senior Sub Engineer, Monitoring and evaluation

Buildings Department, District Multan,

C&W Department, Punjab. Pakistan.

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muhammadusmanmalik@hotmail.com